

ROLES OF NON-TEACHING STAFF IN ACTUALIZING EFFECTIVE TEACHING PRACTICE IN FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ABEOKUTA: ISSUES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract

Teaching Practice is a crucial component of teacher education, providing student-teachers with the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in a practical setting. The teacher trainers cannot single handedly do the work without exposing the trainee to the field. This enables the trainees to have practical experience(s). This is done through Teaching Practice Directorate which is manned by both teaching and non-teaching personnel with diverse roles to play for the overall success of the entire process. This paper addresses the core duties of Teaching Practice Directorate and its non-teaching staff categories roles, contributions and challenges using participant observations and literature review. The paper found challenges like students not abiding by the rules and regulations of the exercise because they did not attend orientation programmes usually organized for them before the commencement of the exercise and non-teaching staff not benefiting from TETFund Teaching Practice allowances, among others. It recommends among others, that students should be attending Teaching Practice orientation before commencing the exercise and that non-teaching staff be included in TETFund Teaching Practice Allowances.

Keywords: Teaching Practice, Non-teaching Staff, Academic Staff, Basic Schools, Teacher Education

Introduction

Teaching practice is a crucial component of teacher education, providing student-teachers with opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in a practical setting. It is a supervised experience where student teachers are placed in real classroom environment to teach and learn from experienced teachers, pupils and the school community. The primary aim of teaching practice is to bridge the gap between theory and practice enabling students-teachers to put into practice the

necessary skills, competence and to imbibe the required confidence in effective teaching under a real-world classrooms.

While the focus is often on the student-teachers and their supervising lecturers, the success of teaching practice exercises relies heavily on the behind-the-scene efforts of non-teaching staff. These individuals including Administrative Officers, and other support staff play vital roles in coordinating the logistics of teaching practice, from securing placement in schools to managing student-teacher deployments. Despite their importance, the contributions of non-teaching staff in facilitating teaching practice are often overlooked.

This article seeks to highlight the critical role that non-teaching staff play in teaching practice in Colleges of Education, and to explore ways in which their efforts could be optimized to enhance quality of teacher education programmes.

Conceptual Clarification

Teacher Education

Teacher Education, according to Afe (1995) refers to the policies, procedures and provision designed to equip prospective teachers with knowledge, attitudes, behaviours and skills they require in performing their tasks effectively in the classroom, school and wider community. The professionals who engage in training the prospective teachers are called teacher educators /teacher trainers.

No Education can rise above the quality of its teachers and teacher education shall continue to be given major emphasis in all education planning and development (NPE, 2004). Afe (1995), defined education as a means to better life of people and uplift the society at large. This means that, a lot of responsibilities are vested on teachers. For an individual teacher to be effective or not, depend on self-perception, the quality of training received in educational institution and the school attended and practicing teaching. This will go a long way in achieving effectiveness.

Teaching, on the other hand, according to Afe (1995) is the systematic process of imparting worthwhile values or helping people to learn. It involves series of interrelated activities capable of changing or modifying the way the learners behave. During teaching activities, the teacher passes information to or organizes events and materials, which the learner interacts with. This is to ensure that learning has taken place by way of manifestation of the desired behaviours in the learners (Afe, 1995).

As it could be deduced from the above, Teacher Education is the process by which a prospective teacher is prepared to handle the various aspects of the teacher's functions like academic, social, psychological and practical function.

Teacher education can therefore simply be defined as the systematic training and productive utilization of a group of persons who by designed orientation and certification are taken as professionals in the transmission of knowledge.

Teacher Education, the National Policy of Education Perspective

The National Policy on Education (2004), states that minimum qualification for entry into teaching profession shall be Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE). The aims and objectives of Teacher Education according to the Policy are highlighted as follows:

- (i) Enhancement of teacher's commitment to the teaching profession;
- (ii) Produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our educational system;
- (iii) Encourage further the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers;
- (iv) Provide teachers with intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and make them adaptable to change situation;
- (v) Help teachers to fit into social life of the community and the society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals.

Teaching Practice Programme in Colleges of Education

Olaitan and Agusiobo (1981), explained that 'teaching practice' is normally used by educationist to refer to the first opportunity the student teacher has to participate in the activities involved in the 'Teaching – Learning situation'. In a broad sense, it is carefully conceived and directed to attain a degree of expertise in understanding the science of pedagogy. Teaching practice entails, among others ensuring that teacher-trainees are posted to Basic Schools to practice how to teach.

Olaitan and Agusiobo (1981), see teaching practice as that phase of the pre – service education of teachers in which the student teacher is given opportunity to bring together educational theory and actual teaching procedures under competent supervision. Ajala (1985) opined that teaching practice is to the prospective teacher as internship is to the medical doctor or apprenticeship is to technician.

Olaitan and Agusiobo (1981), observed that teaching practice as an exercise is based on social constructivist theory concept of cognitive apprentice. They cited Collins, Brown, Newnan (1989), as defining cognitive apprenticeship as learning through – guided experience on cognitive apprenticeship which occurs through legitimate peripheral participation and gradually moves towards full participation.

Olaitan and Agusiobo (1981), further cited Vygostky (1978) who explained that important learning by the child occurs through social interaction with a skillful tutor. The tutor may model behaviour and / or provide verbal instruction for child. This according to them refers to this as co-operative or collaborative dialogue. The child seeks to understand the action or instruction provided by the tutor (often the parents or teacher) then internalizes the information, using it to guide or regulate their own performance.

Akbar (2002) explained that in the context of teaching practice, the child represent the teacher or candidate while the tutor represents the supervisor who through collaborative dialogue, modeling, coaching or mentoring, guides the student teacher into acquiring teaching competencies. That is why he explained that the central issues in learning is becoming a practitioner, not learning about practice.

Akbar (2002) further explained the process of process of Teaching Practice as follows: That Teaching Practice is a Six (6) Unit compulsory course for all students of Colleges of Education. That before these students are posted to different cooperating teaching practice schools, they must have passed related courses like Micro Teaching Theory (EDU 213) and Micro Teaching Practicum (EDU 224). These are the ways which students are exposed to teaching within their group before they are exposed to the real teaching in their Teaching Practice Schools. That the duration of the programme is minimum of 26 weeks as stipulated by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), which is the supervisory body.

That the practical teaching programme takes place immediately after the second year second semester examination and run through the first semester of their third year. That Teaching Practice Programme in Teacher Education Institution is like internship for Pharmacists, Doctors etc and the Industrial Attachment Programme for Polytechnic students before they can qualify to practice the respective professions.

Akbar (2002), further broke down the Aims and Objectives of Teaching Practice into 14 which are as follows:

1. To provide the prospective teachers with an opportunity of establishing an appropriate teacher pupil relationship;
2. To provide an opportunity for evaluating the student potential as a teacher and suitability for the teaching profession;
3. To develop personal relationship with others: administrators, teachers, parents and students;
4. To provide the future teacher with practical experience in school to overcome the problems of discipline and enable him / her to develop method of control;
5. To provide him/her with an opportunity to put theories into practice and to develop a deeper understanding of educational principles and their implications for learning;
6. To enable the student teachers to effectively plan and prepare for lessons;
7. To develop skills in the use of fundamental procedures, techniques and methods of teaching;
8. To develop desirable professional interests, attitudes and ideas relative to teaching profession;
9. To enable student teachers to acquire desirable characteristics/traits of a teacher and to display appropriate behavior;
10. To prepare student teachers with an opportunity to have teaching evaluated and to gain from the benefits of constructive criticism;
11. To provide an opportunity for self-evaluation and to discover own strengths and weaknesses;
12. To develop skills in future teachers related to teaching like fluent speaking, meaningful reading, using black white board and other teaching material;
13. To provide an opportunity to liaise with school environment, its functioning and with community and its resources;
14. To provide for the exchange of ideas and methods between practicing school and teacher training institutions' staff and students, perceiving new ideas, material and equipment in use in practicing schools and introducing new ideas, material and equipments into the school.

Teaching Practice as a Means of Realistic Experience for would-be Teachers

The Minimum Standard of the National commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) (2020) explained the intent behind organizing teaching practice as that it clears the Student teachers' expectations in the area of ethical and professional issues. That it also afford the student teacher opportunity to understand his area of focus during teaching and how to put in place practical activities, mentoring methodology, improvisation of instructional materials, relationship between supervisors, mentors and student teachers.

Organization and Administration of Teaching Practice Exercise

- (a) The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) in the 2020 Revised edition of the Minimum Standard, stipulates that teaching practice should be administered by a Directorate, which shall plan, organize and coordinate the entire Teaching Practice Programme. It is a significant duty of the body to develop, apply and periodically review the Teaching Practice Assessment Booklet, Student Reflective Journal, and Training Manual for Mentors, Lesson plan, etc. The directorate shall also ensure that students are posted to schools of good standing as well as to organize inter and intra institutional workshops, seminars on effective Teaching Practice guidelines and implementation.

Teaching Practice Directorate Organigram

Source: Field Survey (2021)

The Directorate of Teaching Practice is made up of Academic staff and the Non-Teaching Staff as contained in the above organogram of the Line staff as approved by the NCCE.

In between the various levels of the organogram are placed the non-teaching staff providing various supportive roles in terms of administration, connecting units, publicity, protocol and interacting with the various units of the College through approved communication networks.

Responsibilities of the Non-Teaching Staff in the Directorate of Teaching Practice

Odunuga (2020), a one time Teaching Practice Directorate head identified the roles of non-teaching staff in the Teaching Practice programme in a broad form, general administration, logistic and technical support as presented below:

- (i) Register the N. C. E Regular, Part-Time, Sandwich, and PDE students for Teaching Practice Exercise;
- (ii) Register the cooperating schools ;
- (iii) Provide logistics for a successful assessment of the Cooperating School ;
- (iv) Provide general administrative roles like sorting out of forms and posting of students to the cooperating schools;
- (v) Organize sensitization/orientation programme for the Supervisors (lecturers) and students before the commencement of the exercise ;
- (vi) Organize workshop for Head / Teachers of cooperating schools;
- (vii) Collect and organize Academic staff list from Deans of Schools for the purpose of Lecturer's Posting for Teaching Practice Supervision;
- (viii) Preparation of yearly Teaching Practice Transportation Allowance in accordance with guidelines approved by the Provost;
- (ix) Assigned immediate supervisor, internal moderator, external moderators to the students for supervision / moderation of scores;
- (x) Organize workshop for lecturers that are to participate in the yearly teaching practice supervision;
- (xi) Releasing and collection of yearly teaching practice TETFUND forms from lecturers and forwarding of same to the TETFUND Office in Abuja through the Office of the Directorate of Academic Programme in the college;

- (xii) Collation of Teaching Practice Tetfund form submitted by lecturers and forwards same to the Director of Academic Programme for onward transfer to Tetfund Office, Abuja.

Roles of Non –Teaching Staff (Administrative Officers, Executive Officers and Clerical Officers) During Teaching Practice Exercise

The following, amongst others are some of the roles played by the Non-teaching staff (Odunuga, 2020):

- (i) Collate the Teaching Practice Results/scores submitted by all the categories of the supervisors and forward same to the Teaching Practice Coordinator who would then present to the School and Academic Boards for ratification;
- (ii) Submission of the Academic Board approved results to the I. C. T. Centre of the College for input into the College data base;
- (iii) Periodical presentation of teaching practice matters to Teaching Practice Committee for ratification;
- (iv) Performing all other related duties as may be necessary and directed by the Teaching Practice Coordinator from time to time.

Other Roles Performed by Non – Teaching Staff Before, During And After Teaching Practice Exercise

Odunuga (2020), further explained the activities of the Secretary in Teaching Practice Unitas follows:

That such activities include typesetting and printing of variety of documents needed to perfect logistics involved in teaching practice activities such as teaching practice calendar, memos on teaching practice posting; invitation of students, proprietors and supervisors for teaching practice programme as the case may be, score sheets of students and supervisors, student's introduction letter to their Teaching Practice schools, etc

That during Teaching Practice exercise, non-teaching staff engage in typesetting and printing of Teaching practice scores submitted by the immediate supervisors, Internal and External Moderators, drafting of various forms of memos that may be related to Teaching Practice Programme , etc.

That non-teaching staff also impute scores of student at the ICT Centre after it might have been considered by the School Board.

Furthermore, that the task of driving the team of teaching practice officials to Cooperating school for inspections, internal moderators to their places of primary assignment, ensuring neat and hygienic working environment for all concerned in the directorate.

That technical roles are usually imported to the directorate from the Works and services department. Situations warrants stationing a staff for some periods of time in order to allow uninterrupted work flow especially at peak periods. For effectiveness, the head of the non-teaching staff is usually selected from the very senior level of the Registry, preferably an Assistant Deputy Registrar (ADR).

Odunuga (2020), further explained non-teaching staff Teaching Practice in the context of Federal College of Education, Abeokuta as follows:

Challenges Faced by Non-teaching Staff in Teaching Practice Unit in Federal College of Education, Abeokuta

Odunuga (2020), explained that non- teaching staff of Teaching Practice Unit often face some challenges. This study also observed some of these challenges in Federal College of Education, Abeokuta Teaching Practice Unit as follows:

Insufficient Number of Staff in the Unit

The staff in the Unit are not enough when compared with the enormous tasks to be performed. One Secretary is not sufficient for the volume of typesetting task in the Unit.

Uncooperative Attitude of Staff/Parent Requesting for Re-posting of Teaching Practice Students

The time and materials used in changing Teaching Practice students from one school to another is more than initial time and such act often serve as set back to the work of staff in the Unit. This mostly affect, especially, the Secretary that is often overburden to work repeatedly in the course of changing schools.

Attitude of Some Supervisors/Moderators for not Submitting Students Scores at the Appropriate Time for Collation and Further Processing

Some supervisors will collect their Teaching Practice transportation claims but will not go and supervise the students that they have already collected their score sheets and posting list. Some of them may misplace their score sheets and students list and will come for additional score sheets to be supervised. Some may seek for the sort code of their bank when it is the time to fill their TETFUND forms. These are some of the challenges non- teaching staff are facing during their daily activities in the Unit.

Failure of Some Schools to Circulate Student's Scores to Various Departments for Updating of the Departmental Records on Each of the Students

Some schools do not collect and circulate students' scores to departmental exams officers despite the fact that such scores are dispersed to schools by the Unit. Therefore, departments do come to search for such scores directly at the Unit. This process overstretches no-teaching staff of the Unit.

Problems Emanating From Teaching Practice Students

Some Students do not attend orientation programme organized for them before the commencement of the exercise. This used to make them violate some rules and regulations of the exercise during the Teaching Practice exercise.

Some students do refuse to register for the Teaching Practice exercise while some will not inform their parents / guardians their Zone of their choice before submission of their Teaching Practice Form. These sets of students usually present their cases when the work would have been almost completed. To take care of them while posting usually pose problem to the non-teaching staff in terms of time, energy and resources wastage.

Challenges from Head or Staff of Cooperating School

Some school's heads or teachers explain to supervisors when such students teachers are sent on errands from school and the student's supervisors are around for assessment. Some school heads renege in fulfilling their promises to provide accommodation for the students when they register their schools at teaching practice office. Such students' teachers do come back to non-teaching staff for re-posting.

Inadequate Working Tools/Gadgets

The Unit do photocopy lots of documents for distribution to students, cooperating schools and supervisors before, during and after the exercise. However, photocopy machines and other working equipments are not always inadequate.

Non Inclusion of Non-Teaching Staff on TETFund Teaching Practice Allowance

Teaching staff do benefit from TETFund Teaching Practice interventions for performing Teaching Practice functions while non-teaching of the Unite are not included in such interventions.

Conclusion

Based on the above, it could be concluded that some students' do not abide by the rules and regulations of Teaching Practice exercise because they could not attend orientation programmes usually organized for them before the commencement of the exercise.

The secretariat staff of Teaching Practice Unit are not supplied with stationeries regularly to ease their work. Equally, there is often lack of functional equipments like photocopier machine, printer, and desktop computer for the daily activities of the Unit.

There is frequent changing or re-posting of teaching practice students from one school to another which do demoralizes the staff handling such duties and distorts the exercise.

Non-teaching staff working in the Teaching Practice Unit or Directorate are not allowed to participate nor benefit from TETFund intervention for Teaching Practice exercise. This always dampens their morale for efficient work.

Teaching Practice Unit do share project vehicle with other schools and units.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, this paper recommends as follows:

1. Students' should be attending Teaching Practice orientation before commencing the exercise.
2. There should be regular supply of stationeries to ease the work of secretariat staff of the Unit.
3. There is need to reduce changing or re-posting of teaching practice students from one school to another. This is because such practice do demoralizes the staff handling such duties and distorts the exercise.
4. Non-teaching staff working in the Teaching Practice Unit or Directorate should also be allowed to participate and benefit from TETFund intervention for Teaching Practice exercise. This will boost their morale and propel them to do more.
5. There is need for provision of functional equipments like photocopier machine, printer, and desktop computer for the daily activities of the Unit in delivering prompt services.
6. There is need for provision of project van for Teaching Practice Unit for effective running of the Unit.

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